

THE VULNERABILITY OF NIGERIAN ECONOMY AND THE AFRICAN CONTINENTAL FREE TRADE AREA AGREEMENT PROTOCOL ON FREE MOVEMENT OF PEOPLE AND GOODS: AN EXPOSITION

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Nigeria,
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Abstract: *The foregoing, this study investigated the vulnerability of Nigerian economy and the African continental free trade area agreement protocol on free movement of people and goods. The study was qualitative in nature as data was gotten from secondary sources of textbooks, the Internet, library, magazine, newspaper, while the theory of neo-functionalism which is an important component parts of the broad theory of integration were adopted as the framework of analysis. The study established that the Nigerian economy is vulnerable to the African Continental Free Trade Area Agreement on free movement of people and goods. The study recommends among other things that: there is need for Nigeria to incorporate the collaboration and initiatives of both the private and public sectors to invest in cross-border infrastructure of the country which will help in closing up Nigeria's physical infrastructure gap which already requires a huge capital investment as well as the revenue losses in smuggling, dumping and illicit trade flows. Nigeria has to ensure strict implementation of the removal of non-tariff barriers, promote the convergence on regulatory measures, and encourage greater trade facilitation among the participating states. The African Union is encouraged to entrench a rule-based economic governance structure and improve their institutional capacities to promptly settle possible trade dispute that would arise from the implementation of the AfCFTA as well as address issues of unfair trade practices.*

Introduction

Generally, most scholars affirm that the AfCFTA deal will provide strong measures for effective

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liberalization of trade and reduce trade costs in order to give consumers the opportunity to have access to more products at affordable prices within the African sub-region. It is believed that primary products and raw materials that are imported and other intermediate inputs will enhance competitive trade among local manufacturers and promote economic value chain on the continent. This will be achieved by creating the right market environment for greater competitive pressure to enhance producers efficiency and in turn stimulate greater access to African markets with mutual gains and benefits (Saygili, Peters and Knebel, 2018; Cazares, 2019).

Nigeria was among the last 11 groups of states that signed the AfCFTA Agreement after a lingered political hesitation despite being a significant player in the region and the most populous country in Africa with a population of about 200 million – controlling a GDP of about US\$376 billion which represents 17% of Africa's GDP. Nigeria is widely perceived at the global stage as a protectionist country, owing to its weak industrial base, low productive capacity and infant manufacturing sector that cannot survive stiffer competition at the continental and global markets. There are also serious concerns regarding Nigeria's over-concentration on oil exports with less diversification of non-oil exports (The Economist, 22 March 2018).

However, for Onwunyi, U.M; Asukwo, A.A, B and Ojukwu, S (2024), there are concerns whether the AfCFTA agreement has strong measures to check anti-competitive actions, including dumping which occurs when a particular state reduces the cost of its export goods below the cost of production in order to have undue market advantage (Vanguard News, November 8, 2018). Although AfCFTA Agreement has framework and mechanisms for dispute settlement, but its effectiveness in offering adequate protection to local manufacturers over discriminatory and hostile trade practices is a major source of worry for Nigerian leadership (The Conversation, July 26, 2018).

Indeed, Nigeria's dependent on mainly oil exports, with little or no export diversification on non-oil sectors of the economy is expected to deny it such long-term growth benefits accruable from the AfCFTA Agreement. Stuart (2019) argues that an unstable export market economy, without a sustainable export and industrial diversification would be vulnerably exposed to stiffer competition at the regional market bloc that it cannot survive. While temporary economic boom for local commodity exporters may occur in times of increased intra-regional trade, the economic benefits will not lead to any long-term sustainable gains. Therefore in the case of Nigeria which operates mono-economy, the AfCFTA deal may offer some temporary

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benefits that may become stagnant or even result to negative growth.

Again considering the absence of an adequate trade facilitation policy, especially the issue of rules of origin, AfCFTA may open Africa's borders to cheap products from world trade powers like China. Cheap products from Europe and Asia – especially China, that are imported to Cameroon or Ghana may ultimately cross many porous African borders and finally find its way into Nigeria. This problem which has been in existence due to Africa's porous borders will definitely get worsened following the operation of the AfCFTA (Crabtree, 2018).

Particularly, as with other African countries, Nigeria faces serious border problems, with the existence of a vast uncontrolled and un-police able borders, including as many as 1,400 illegal transit routes, that facilitate the influx of illegal migrants who mostly crossover for illegal activities other than legitimate trade (Agboton-Johnson, Ebo, and Mazal, 2004). Nigeria's key challenge in this aspect stems from the possibility of illicit movement of persons and goods, including illicit financial flows (IFF) which average to 25% of developing countries trade (Stuart, 2019b). These illicit inflows continue to deprive Nigeria its expected trade revenue that could be reinvested in the economy to achieve more industrial development and export-diversification.

Literature Review

ACFTA Protocol on Free Movement of People and Goods and Nigeria's Border Control

Van der Nest (2019), argues that intra-movement (including goods) and migration of people in the region are already predominant and substantial. Van der Nest (2019) further makes a case that most African countries have already put adequate measures together toward implementing free movement of people and goods on the continent and that the success recorded so far would make it less difficult for the AfCFTA Agreement on the same agenda to succeed. However, with the free trade area, it becomes difficult for African states to control its borders and enforce effective controls on external customs.

Stuart (2019b) investigates the level of illicit flow of finance in Africa, which average about 25% of the developing country trade in the last decade. The poor level of border governance and security encourage large flows of illicit trade within the African boundaries. Hence, for African nations to make real economic progress it will have to ensure effective border control and governance to curtail the flow of illegal goods and commodities across the boundaries. The need for export specialization according to different country categorizations will help to understand the nature of illegal crossing of goods across different national borders. African nations can still diversify their economies in two different

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categories of export specialization such as extractive commodity exporters (including fuels, minerals, and metals) and residual/agricultural exporters.

World Economic Forum on Africa (2019) maintains that the objective of the AfCFTA is to establish a common market system in the African region to benefit the countries therein numbering about 54 states. The main idea according to the report is to promote free movement of people and goods across the states, particularly, business operators and travelers who invest in other countries, so as to develop a custom union on the continent. A fully operational custom union in African region will greatly boost trade and investment in the region at the long-run. There will also be job opportunities for the 1.27 billion people that make up Africa. Hence, Nigeria's involvement in the AfCFTA is seen as a welcome development.

Irwin (1996) believes that the purpose of any free trade agreement whether at the regional, continental level or world level is to boost economic growth and ensure free movement of people and goods including factors of production among the countries involved in the agreement. In other words, agreements that facilitate free trade and movement of people across countries with barriers, quotas, tariffs and other strict government economic policies already eliminated will entrench international trade liberalization. Moreover, this will help

participating countries to specialize mainly on production of goods and services that they have relative advantage to produce over other states. Such leads to increased income stream of the country (Irwin 1996).

Indeed, as with other African countries, Nigeria faces serious border problems, with the existence of a vast uncontrolled and un-policeable borders, including as many as 1,400 illegal transit routes, that facilitate the influx of illegal migrants who mostly crossover for illegal activities other than legitimate trade (Agboton-Johnson, Ebo, and Mazal, 2004). Nigeria's key challenge in this aspect stems from the possibility of illicit movement of persons and goods, including illicit financial flows (IFF) which average to 25% of developing countries trade (Stuart, 2019b). These illicit inflows continue to deprive Nigeria its expected trade revenue that could be reinvested in the economy to achieve more industrial development and export-diversification.

Kutiya (2016) observes that there are still obvious physical and social infrastructure constraints and gaps that must have to be fixed and covered for African countries to fully maximize the economic benefits of AfCFTA and also the great need to involve both public and private efforts to make investments on cross-border infrastructure in Africa. This will resolve the obvious physical infrastructure gap in Africa and since such is a substantial programme of

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investment, it will demand huge financial involvement which is expected to gulp at least about \$93 billion per year.

Meanwhile, UNCTAD data indicates that foreign direct investment in Africa has expanded tremendously by more than six times from an estimated \$90 billion in 1995 to \$700 billion in 2014. However, the continuation of this economic achievement on the continent will critically depend on Africa's national governments and stakeholders in the private and public business sector to coordinate efforts in ensuring that this economic progress continues to increase substantially especially by making significant infrastructural investments such as electricity, social and environmental security, information and communications technology (ICT), and cross-border facilities, etc. Kutiya (2016) notes that particularly, provision of cross-border facilities which are seen as soft infrastructure is very important across African countries especially to make customs checks more efficient across African national borders (Onwunyi, Asukwo & Ojukwu, 2024). The best approach to utilized to achieve the best result would be to adopt a bottom-up strategy which involves maximizing the contributions and opinions of border communities and that of SMEs that operate across the borders, specific method of setting some standard guidelines will also be very useful in managing border control and governance.

Theoretical Orientations

This paper is anchored on the Neofunctionalism which proposed the idea of regional integration which is mainly derived from the work of David Mitrany. Neofunctionalism critically addressed the immediate process of integration among the state especially within the broad spectrum of regional integration. It was observed that initially the states pursue or have integration in limited functional or economic spheres. Although partially integrated countries connect to increasing levels of integration in related aspects. The product of integration is regarded as 'spill over' by the neofunctionalists. This spill over can occur in two dimensions: functional and political. While functional spillover deals with the inter-linkages of various economic sectors and aspects, including integration in one policy aspect spilling across into others; the political spillover deals with the establishment of supranational governance machinery such as the EU and African Union to supervise the process of integration at the regional level and how states are complying in line with specified policy areas of the integration agreements (Rosamond, 2000; Caporaso, 1998).

Regional integration from the neofunctionalist view was also mainly driven by Ernest B Haas and Jean Monnet's approach to the European integration (Moravcsik, 2005). The European integration was targeted to bind together individual sectors in order to achieve some form

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of spillover effects that promote the idea of integration. More importantly, the neofunctionalist perspective of integration proposed a form of integration that is not based on normative approach but explains the integration process based on empirical data. Generally, integration is an inevitable chain of international process that promotes regional integration rather than mere state of affairs that is desired by states, which could be introduced by leaders (Haas, 1964; Rosamond, 2000)

However, the weakness of the functional and neofunctional theories of integration is that it conceptualized integration as a linear process which made it impossible to make some explanation over some of the setbacks that are inevitable in the process of regional integration. From the foregoing discussions therefore, it means that a country such as Nigeria that has not been able to interlink its various economic sub-sectors and aspects, including backward and forward linkages, will not effectively and significantly benefit from the gains of AfCFTA. Nigeria is setback with underdeveloped industrial and manufacturing sector which impinge on its ability to have diversified export trade. Such weak industrial base and mono-economy limits its capacity and prospects of maintaining sustainable economic growth in the course of implementation of AfCFTA. In addition, Nigeria's prospects under the AfCFTA will be worse considering its porous borders with

no effective border-control mechanisms thereby allowing for the influx of illegal goods into the country. This potentially results to loss of huge tax revenues and could lead to dumping. This explains that Nigeria has very gloomy picture ahead of the implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Area.

Methodology

This research was based on *ex-post facto* research design which is a method of presenting likely antecedents of events that have happened and cannot, therefore, engineered or manipulated by the investigator (Cooper and Schindler, 2001).

This paper was based on qualitative data collection method. The data and information used are mainly sourced from books, journal articles, periodic reviews, internet materials, newspaper reports, and official documents and reports on African free trade issues. These include data from United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA), Brookings Institute, World Bank reports, African Union, AfCFTA agreement, World Economic Forum, PricewaterhouseCoopers, Chatham House, UNCTAD, Manufacturing Association of Nigeria, etc. This paper adopted the qualitative descriptive method of data analysis. The qualitative descriptive analytical method is used to make descriptive analysis and explanation on information that is generated in research so as to build an empirical connection between the

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independent and dependent variables of the study.

Operation of ACFTA Protocol on Intra-regional Free Movement of People and Goods and Nigeria's Border Control

The ACFTA Agreement is the world's largest free trade zone since the beginning of the World Trade Organization. It promises to economically integrate the 55 AU member states, including a market of over 1.2 billion people, which have a unified GDP of worth over US\$3.4 trillion. It is estimated that with the removal of import duties, and establishment of free trade area, AfCFTA can boost intra-African trade by 52.3 percent by the year 2022, and this trade volume will be doubled if there are adequate reductions in non-tariff barriers (Witschge, 2018; Crabtree, 2018; Tralac, 2019).

The goal of establishing a common market for intra-Africa trade with free movement of people and investments is an enduring purpose for instituting the AfCFTA Agreement by AU member states. The AfCFTA deal is therefore viewed as an economic package that will stimulate and create a Custom Union by removing all trade barriers including tariff and non-tariff barriers within the African continent. The agreement relies on its creation of free movement of people and goods to hit its target to boost intra-African trade by accelerating strong

harmonization and coordination of trade liberalization and economic policies across the various African states, and particularly among the various Regional Economic Communities (RECs) (The Economic Commission for Africa, 2018). By so doing AfCFTA will encourage competitive trade both in terms of investment and human enterprise especially by exploiting vast opportunities for industrial production, continental market access and efficient management of state resources (Tralac, 2019).

It is obvious that the overall goal of any free trade agreement both at the regional, continental level or world level is to boost economic growth and ensure free movement of people and goods including factors of production among the countries involved in the agreement (Balistreri, Tarr, and Yonezawa, 2015). Thus, any agreements that facilitate free trade and movement of people across countries with barriers, quotas, tariffs and other strict government economic policies already eliminated will entrench international trade liberalization. Moreover, this will help participating countries to specialize mainly on production of goods and services that they have relative advantage to produce over other states. Such leads to increased income stream of the country (Irwin 1996; Balistreri, Tarr, and Yonezawa, 2015).

It is however a great source of worry that Nigeria faces serious border problems, with the existence

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of a vast uncontrolled and un-policeable borders, including as many as 1,400 illegal transit routes, that facilitate the influx of illegal migrants who mostly crossover for illegal activities other than legitimate trade (Agboton-Johnson, Ebo, and Mazal, 2004). Considering the realities of Nigeria's highly vulnerable borders, the possibility of illicit movement of persons and goods, including illicit financial flows (IFF) which average to 25% of developing countries trade (Stuart, 2019b) becomes imminent. These illicit inflows continue to deprive Nigeria its expected trade revenue that could be reinvested in the economy to achieve more industrial development and export-diversification.

Accordingly, Odikpo and Onwunyi (2020), the strong concern and apprehensions over the implementation of AfCFTA's holistic/comprehensive free trade provisions, including free movement of people and goods is part of the reasons that informed Nigerian government's restraint and delay in committing promptly to the AfCFTA deal. This is particularly in consideration of its porous borders and the possibility of enormous economic and trade losses, as well as tax revenue losses that will be incurred in the long-run which will take huge economic tolls on the country's already palpitating economy. For example, Nigeria was among the last 11 groups of states that signed the AfCFTA Agreement after a lingered political

hesitation despite being a significant player in the region and the most populous country in Africa with a population of about 200 million – controlling a GDP of about US\$376 billion which represents 17% of Africa's GDP. Therefore, the AfCFTA open-ended provisions on free trade area would have strong implications on Nigeria's economy based on its peculiar border realities – including commodity smuggling and illegal financial and trade flows across its border. We shall examine these issues in the coming discussions.

Commodity Smuggling Across Nigerian Borders and the Prospects of Implementation of the AfCFTA Agreement

Generally, only but little progress has been recorded in Nigeria's attempt to promote free trade policies due to its traditional economic practices based on trade protectionism. Golub (2012) noted that Nigeria maintains one of the most vibrant protectionist counties of the world with stiff trade rules and policies that protect its local industries and manufacturers. Therefore the opening of trade borders in the name of free trade has rarely been practiced by Nigerian government. Nigeria has very high profile of bans on importation of goods and services. Box I shows a list of Nigeria's import ban on variety of import commodities, while table 1 shows Nigeria's restricted imports 1995-2017 (Tariff Rates in % or Bans).

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Box 1: Nigeria's Import Prohibition List, 2008-2017

Category 1 – Items	Category 2 – Items
Frozen poultry Meat (beef, pork, lamb, etc.)	Used car tyres
Eggs	Corrugated paper, paper boards, and boxes
Vegetable oils and fats	Toilet paper and facial tissues
Spaghetti-noodles	Yard goods fabrics of all types and articles
Fruit juice in retail packs	of clothing Footwear and bags of leather
Waters without added sugar	and plastic
Waters with added sugar	Hollow glass bottles for beverages
Bagged cement	Used air conditioners and compressors
Medicaments (various ones)	Used motor vehicles over 10 years old
Used pharmaceuticals	Furniture
Finished soaps	Electric generators sound proof casings
Mosquito repellent coils	Gaming machines
Plastics	Ball point pens
Tooth picks	Telephone re-charge cards

Source: Adapted from Golub (2012); Nigerian Customs document, provided by The World Bank.

Table 1: Selected Import Barriers in Nigeria, 1995–2007 (Tariff Rates in % or Bans)

S/N	Items	1995	1997	1999	2001	2003	2005	2007	2018
1	Edible oil	Banned	Banned	55	40	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned
2	Poultry meat	Banned	Banned	55	75	Banned	Banned	Banned	Banned
3	Beer	Banned	Banned	100	100	100	Banned	Banned	Banned
4	Wine	100	100	100	100	100	20	20	-
5	Milk products	55	55	50	50	100	20	20	-
6	Tomato preserves	45	45	45	45	45	20	20	-
7	Used clothes	Banned	-						
8	Tyres	Banned	-						

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9	Wheat dough	Banned	-						
10	Used cars	Banned	Banned/ 70						
11	Sugar	10	10	10	40	100	50	50	70
12	Cloth and apparel	Banned	60	65	55	100	Banned	Banned	45/ Forex ban
13	Tobacco and cigarettes	90	90	80	80	100	50	50	95
14	Rice	100	50	50	75	110	50	50	Banned

Source: Adapted from Golub (2012); Golub, Mbaye and Golubski (2019); Nigerian Customs document, provided by The World Bank.

The tables above show clearly the profile of Nigeria's import ban and portrays the fact that Nigeria has been at the forefront in implementation of very strict trade barriers and restriction policies in Africa and the world market in general. Although Nigeria has fairly and relatively developed productive and economic structures compared with some other smaller countries within the West African sub-region, including Togo, Benin Republic, Ghana etc, it still grapples with the prolonged problems of inefficient and underdeveloped and industrial base. Nigeria's manufacturing sector as well as its agricultural productivity remains limited and lacking sustainable growth. The reality therefore is that most local firms, stakeholders and

powerful interest units favour protectionist policies of the government. Thus, for Onwunyi and Mba (2025), any trade agreements that attempt to foster enhanced free trade that will collapse the long existing trade barriers are often kicked against by the manufacturing sector operatives in Nigeria who mainly feel they cannot withstand the competitive trade that comes with open borders.

However, the key concern that makes the issue more complex is the vulnerability of Nigeria's borders with entry points that are rarely effectively governed and policed by relevant authorities. This inadequacy and/or weakness has been unduly exploited by trans-border traders who utilized the opportunity to cross/smuggle banned goods from neighbouring countries into Nigeria without fulfilling any

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required custom procedures (Raballand and Mjekiqi, 2010).

World Bank reports that commodities that are imported for use in neighbouring countries such as Benin Republic and Togo always find their ways into Nigeria through smuggling and trade diversion. The smugglers take advantage of lower tariff rates in these countries to smuggle the goods into Nigeria even after paying the import duties in those countries. This opportunity arises because of Nigeria high protectionist policies that slam very high tariff rates on importers. So these importers finding it difficult to do business in Nigeria rather engage in port diversion and import their goods into neighbouring countries with cheap tariff rates only to divert it into Nigeria through smuggling thereby taking advantage of Nigeria's unfortunate porous borders which have been poorly governed despite claims of Nigeria's trade protectionism. It is therefore more lucrative for importers especially those importing cars. Some of the products implicated in the acts of smuggling through Nigeria's neighbouring countries include: frozen foods (including chicken, turkey), second hand clothing, sugar and wheat, cigarettes as well as foreign rice (World Bank, 2009; World Bank, 2010).

Generally, smugglers always maintain very sophisticated and well-coordinated networks, with many middle agents being used in the business (Golub and Maybe, 2009; Bhagwati and

Hansen, 1973). They maintain high levels of trust among themselves and coordinate their activities through well-organized informal networks through which the illegal trade is connected to different trade areas and regions with capital returns and funds transfers well-managed. One of the factors that sustain the smuggling trade is the availability of large demanding markets in Nigeria to patronize the smuggled products especially the used cars, second-hand clothing, frozen foods etc (Raballand and Mjekiqi, 2010; Fishman and Wei, 2004). There are always local representative who handle the smuggled second-hand products such as used cars once it enters into Nigeria through the higher agents who make the transshipment. These commodities are readily smuggled through the numerous land or sea borders/routes in Nigeria, numbering over 1400 which are rarely monitored or checked by the relevant body such as the Nigerian custom probably because of their informal locations like in the deep forests and very swampy areas, including those on mountain top.

There could be as many as 1,400 illegal transit routes which form a network of roads: Southwest – Idi-Iroko in the Egbado area of Ogun state and Seme in Lagos state; the south-south – the port city of Warri in Delta state; and the north-east – the borders of Adamawa, Borno, and Yobe states which they share with Niger and Cameroon (Agboton-Johnson, Ebo, and Mazal, 2004). Despite mounting control posts, the laxity and

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corrupt practices by some immigration officials, who often collude with illegal immigrants to gain entry, continue to undermine effective control and checks on migrant populations (Adaawen, 2017). The large uncontrolled and un-policeable borders facilitate the influx of illegal commodities and migrants who mostly crossover for illegal activities other than legitimate trade.

However, customs officers are spread across the paths of smugglers but they are readily 'officially' settled but how effective such monies collected/generated are duly remitted to the government is quite a great concern. It is no doubt that such customs practices indicate a very poor border governance system which aids corruption and lack of accountability. Smugglers prefer to have low valuations and make unofficial payments on their smuggled products on transit than to face the high tariffs in the formal border entry points (Raballand and Mjekiqi, 2010; Deardorff and Stolper, 1990).

It is therefore on the bases of the foregoing that the prospects of the ACFTA become very bleak for Nigeria. The practice of smuggling has more or less become very accepted trade practice in Nigeria. Even the neighbouring countries including Togo and Benin where most of the goods are being smuggled from have made such transshipment practices (i.e. re-exportation of imported goods) a formal trade practice which has now become a major source of their income. Even though these counties collect low tariffs,

the high rate of turnovers makes it more lucrative for these countries. Transshipment or re-exportation is now more favourable and valued with more revenues accruing to the involved countries than the goods they locally manufactured and export from their own countries. For instance, Benin and Togo made as much as over 60% gross GDP from this form of re-export trade in 2008. It has also been observed that such re-export trade creates employment opportunities for many people working at the port as they handle movement and transportation of goods which go in and out of the re-exporting countries' port (Golub, 2012). Unfortunately, this form of trade does not benefit Nigeria. It rather results to huge losses in givernemtn revenue. Meanwhile those firms who the import bans are meant for rather operate at a very low level that they cannot engage in production of the large quantity of goods needed in the country such as rice and not to talk of producing enough for exportation. This is the reason why such goods are easily smuggled to readily available market in Nigeria. The unchecked act of smuggling is as a result of lack of effective border governance in Nigeria and it encourages evasion of import duties, cuts down tax revenue and breeds corruption – all these affect Nigeria's economy negatively.

Considering Nigeria's long existing border problems, it is therefore worrisome and most likely that the introduction and implementation

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of ACFTA free movement of goods and people will rather worsen the already bad scenario, lead to huge government tax revenue losses, and jeopardize Nigeria's economic fortunes. Meanwhile, it is quite doubtful if the introduction of ACFTA without clearly stamping out smuggling will improve Nigeria's intra-trade engagements in Africa. Nigeria's share of intra-African trade cannot be viable if it is built on smuggling and border corruption and the continuation of such illicit trade practices will fundamental blanket the prospects of Nigeria's economic gains through ACFTA at the long-run. It is particularly noted that Nigeria's protectionist trade policies encourage the prevalence of commodity smuggling into the country. Therefore in a bid to exert once again its trade protectionist tendencies, the Buhari led government closed down Nigerian land borders in 2018. This was done to disallow the movement of all goods through the land borders and more especially prevent commodity smuggling in order to raise internal production. Golub, Mbaye and Golubski (2019) maintain that informal cross-border trade (ICBT) has become a common practice across African markets, especially in West Africa region as a result of the artificial and often porous borders, weak enforcement of border controls, corruption and poor coordination of economic policies and trade rules among neighbouring states.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Considering Nigeria's long existing border problems, the introduction and implementation of AfCFTA free movement of goods and people will rather worsen the already bad scenario, lead to huge government tax revenue losses, and jeopardize Nigeria's economic fortunes. Meanwhile, it is quite doubtful if the introduction of AfCFTA without clearly stamping out smuggling will improve Nigeria's intra-trade engagements in Africa. Nigeria's share of intra-African trade cannot be viable if it is built on smuggling and border corruption and the continuation of such illicit trade practices will fundamental blanket the prospects of Nigeria's economic gains through AfCFTA at the long-run. This implies that Nigeria's prospects under the AfCFTA will be worse considering its porous borders with no effective border-control mechanisms thereby allowing for the influx of illegal goods into the country. This potentially results to loss of huge tax revenues and could lead to dumping. This explains that Nigeria has very gloomy picture ahead of the implementation of the African Continental Free Trade Area.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are expedient and useful:

1. The African Union should entrench a rule-based economic governance structure and improve their institutional capacities to promptly settle possible trade dispute that would

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arise from the implementation of AfCFTA as well as address issues of unfair trade practices, such as dumping – and ensure that no countries lowers the sales of their exports below the cost of production to gain unfair market share.

2. Nigeria must work in synergy with the African Union to ensure that the gains from the

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AfCFTA are fairly and equitably distributed and minimize trade losses. This will help in actualizing the goal of making AfCFTA formidable strategy for sustainable economic growth and development for the African continent.

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